

LEADING MODERN TRENDS IN VOCATIONAL EDUCATION IN THE TRAINING OF SPECIALISTS

Mirjanova Nargiza Norkulovna

1st year doctoral student of the Institute of Pedagogical Innovations, vocational education,
retraining and advanced training of teaching staff,
Tashkent, Republic of Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *Vocational education and training is a system under strong pressure from the global transformational processes of recent decades. Technological innovations are causing rapid changes in the types and content of jobs in the national economy. The demand for qualifications and new skills is constantly changing. The open market causes the expansion of employment opportunities for the individual both at the national and international levels, and the complexity of the demand for new skills in the labor market is fundamentally changing the structure, organization and content of vocational education and training. Vocational education generates the largest number of future workforce and future university students. That's why, the socio-economic importance of vocational education and training is constantly at the center of attention of political and professionals from all over the world.*

Keywords : *vocational education, training, trend, specialist, employment, quality.*

New times require new skills. New times require a new approach to vocational education and training, as well as the ability and ability to effectively create new and real benefits in people's lives, in the economy and society in which they live. This is a key aspect of the development of vocational education and training in the future.

In his message to the parliament for 2023, the President of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev focused on the problems of education. 2023 has been declared the year of “Care for the Human Being and Quality Education”. It is necessary to continue the initiated reforms in this area and improve the quality of education in educational institutions .

Therefore, addressing the challenges of raising the level of education has great potential to stimulate human development.

Priority areas for human development by 2030 should take into account a number of problems in the field of education, with a main focus on :

- 1) Increasing enrollment in higher education, which is relatively low in the world.
- 2) Improving the quality of education and professional competence of teaching staff. It is also necessary to improve the positions of universities in Central Asia and Uzbekistan in international university rankings, such as Quacquarelli Symonds and selected disciplinary fields, most notably STEM (Science , Technology , Engineering , Mathematics).
- 3) Reducing the share of public spending on education, while increasing the share of the private sector in education.
- 4) The reduction of gender inequality, which is observed at all levels of the education system, but is especially pronounced in the higher education system.
- 5) Increasing the innovative aspect and quality of state institutions.

6) Uzbekistan does not use the potential to attract foreign students to its universities, the number of foreign students studying at the universities of Uzbekistan did not exceed 0.2% of university students.

Such reforms can bring a number of benefits to vocational education:

- equity and increased access to quality vocational education and training, higher education and research with due regard to quality assurance;
- providing flexible learning paths, as well as recognition, validation and accreditation of knowledge, skills and competencies acquired through formal and non-formal education;
- that all young people and adults, especially girls and women, achieve appropriate and recognized functional levels of literacy, numeracy and acquired life skills provided by adult learning, education and training opportunities;
- to advance science, technology and innovation.

Information and communication technologies (ICTs) should be used to promote education systems, dissemination of knowledge, access to information, quality and effective learning, and more efficient service delivery.

In this context, a commitment was made to increase public spending on education, according to the context of the countries, to no less than 4-6% of gross domestic product and/or no less than 15-20% of total public spending on education. "Transforming Vocational Education and Training", based on the Shanghai Forum 2012, the following questions were rightly asked: Who is the agent of change? How should vocational education and training respond? How can vocational education and training opportunities be improved? How can vocational education and training be transformed to reach its full potential? This means that the transformation of vocational education and training must be achieved by changing old paradigms and applying new tools. The new vocational education and training must be transformed into an attractive system with improved reputation, position and value, and in line with its own ideas and potential.

An important trend in vocational education is its internationalization and integration, which leads to the rapprochement of countries, and the creation of conditions for the formation of a global educational space. Today, there are many open educational systems that provide professional educational services, regardless of distances and state borders. The need for continuous education is due to both the human need for self-development, and the progress of science and technology. Innovations in vocational education are the most important systemically self-organizing innovations aimed at evolution vocational education.

Vocational education and training should improve the access of young people and adults to opportunities for changing needs of the labor market and life in general, reducing poverty and social disparities, and supporting the idea of a sustainable and peaceful future.

Recently, in the context of workforce development in the developed countries of the world, such as Canada, Australia, Germany, Singapore and Japan, several key strategies focused on vocational education and training have been applied:

- promotes and markets vocational education and training as a viable alternative to more traditional models of promotion and education. This is achieved by integrating competency-based learning with academic institutions at the secondary and higher education levels;
- adoption of the National Qualifications Framework, including all levels of education and training;
- creation of the National Labor Certification-Licensing Program;

- development of industry standards and bodies in all sectors;
- creation of an independent Labor Market Observatory;
- providing reports on the labor market on an ongoing basis - both on the demand side and on the supply side ;
- development of the vocabulary of the profession in accordance with international standards;
- establishing mechanisms for identifying, classifying, training and certifying people in the informal sector;
- providing training opportunities for entrepreneurship and innovation;
- expanding employment opportunities and participation of vulnerable groups - young workers, persons with disabilities, older laid-off workers and “closed” population groups;
- the establishment of a National Training Fund with the participation of the government and the private sector;
- adoption of legislation on funding, accreditation, standard setting and quality assurance in the national education system;
- development of modern programs of practical training and practical exercises;
- providing career information and related career guidance.

In general, efforts are concentrated in several key areas of vocational education and training:

1. Increase the relevance of vocational education and training
2. Increasing access and improving quality
3. Adjusting qualifications and developing different learning paths
4. Improve management and expand partnerships
5. Increase investment in vocational education and training and find different ways to finance

The contribution of vocational education and training in areas such as youth employment , sustainable development and e-learning is gaining recognition and relevance. The question remains how to transform the vocational education and training sector in order to increase its potential.

Thus, today there is an urgent need for high-quality professional education. An effective education system is vital to the continued development of any country and the long-term prosperity of society.

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